

IMPACT FACTOR: 7.86

ISSN0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

13 Years of Open Access

Vol. 13 Issue-VI DECEMBER 2022

Bi-monthly Peer-Reviewed e-Journal

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ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Why Did Moses Kill Mary? Or Did Moses Kill Mary?: A Psychological Study of Doris Lessing's *The Grass is Singing*

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Article History: Submitted-22/10/2022, Revised-23/12/2022, Accepted-24/12/2022, Published-31/12/2022.

Abstract:

In her debut novel *The Grass is Singing*, Doris Lessing, a British writer who borrows the title of the novel from T.S. Eliot's *The Waste Land*, gradually unknots the obvious insipidity of the romantic connotation of the title in reality. In 1950, Lessing's profoundly personal manuscript got transformed into the novel itself. The novel, being set in 1940's Rhodesia, opens in dramatic fashion with a small news report indicating that Mary Turner, the wife of a White-British Rhodesian farmer Dick Turner, had been found murdered on her verandah. The novel goes on to unveil the annihilation of the coherent "self" of Mary Turner, due to the interplay of several external forces. It actually "traces her decay into death". This current paper aims at focusing how the novel exhibits the remarkable congruence in its encoding of race and culture and to show if it truly succeeds in reinforcing colonial fantasies of racial and sexual otherness. This paper also strives to answer the mysterious question - "why was Mary killed by Moses? Or was it Moses who killed Mary?" from a postcolonial perspective.

Keywords: Postcolonial Studies; Power; Psychological turmoil; Racial & Sexual other; Inferiority Complex.

MURDER MYSTERY

By special correspondent

Mary Turner, wife of Richard Turner, a farmer at Ngesi, was found murdered on the front verandah of their homestead yesterday morning. The houseboy, who has been arrested, has confessed to the crime. No motive has

been discovered. It is thought he was in search of valuables. (Lessing 9)

Doris Lessing's first realistic novel *The Grass is Singing* starts off with the above-mentioned news report by an anonymous 'special correspondent' (Lessing 9). Lessing believes that, unlike the journalist, 'collecting facts and information', a keen reader 'has to go inwards to probe out the truth' (Going Home). Being the protagonist and the wife of a White-Rhodesian farmer, Mary Turner went through a series of psychological trauma, and it is true to their black servant Moses as well. This paper aims to deal with the psychological turmoil faced by Mary and Moses and to solve the riddle of the mysterious murder.

In the 1890's the British South African Company claimed rights to land through treaty, occupation and conquest. As the pioneers and other early white colonists became disenchanted with Rhodesia's mineral potential, they shifted their focus of interest to extensive land use through land speculation, ranching and cultivation (Pollak). One such White farmer was Dick Turner, who got trapped in the rack of colonialism. He was a young and promising farmer, and quite amiable with the native Blacks. While Dick was portrayed as a socialist figure, his wife Mary was presented as a racist. She used to hate every aspect of the natives and was cruel with them; every little fault was punished and in a short time she altered dozens of servants:

She hated their half-naked, thick-muscled black bodies stooping in the mindless rhythm of their work. She hated their sullenness, their averted eyes when they spoke to her, their veiled insolence; and she hated more than anything, with a violent physical repulsion, the heavy smell that came from them, a hot, sour animal smell. (Lessing 100)

Mary, the child of unhappy parents (the father a drunkard and the mother rendered frustrated and bitter through poverty), succeeds in creating a comfortable *modus vivendi* for herself by doing secretarial work and living in a "girls'" club. She used to be "a good pal" to her men and women friends and was content to remain unmarried (Lessing 30). At age thirty she still wore 'her hair little-girl fashion on her shoulders, and... little-girl frocks in pastel colors, and [keeps] her shy, naive manner' (Lessing 31). Her seamless routine and her peace of mind got

destroyed one evening when she overheard gossip about herself. Mary ultimately ends up marrying Dick. The initial years of their wedding are not too happy, since Mary had problems adjusting to the new rural environment as she was used to the amenities available in the city. She meets the black house-servant Samson. She begins to display a deep aversion towards Dick for his generosity to Samson, which she feels is undeserved. She wreaks havoc by taking control of the household and gets so tight-fisted that Samson is forced to resign. These acts raise the already acceleratory tensions rise between Mary and Dick, as he grows peeved with her misuse of precious water and he is tormented with the lack of physical affection she had for him. She starts doubting Dick as he turns into an apiarist. Later on, he pounds over several business strategies but none of them came out with good result. At one point her discontent reaches such an extent that she hastens back to the city where she had been so contended before. Being a married woman, she did not have favorable treatment in the city, and had to return with Dick meekly and uncomplainingly. Love and despair both were the ingredients of their relationship.

Mary's psychological momentum should not be neglected here. It is important to see that the source of her eventual breakdown is shown years before, in her ordered alienation from herself. Her inability to handle the black servants- a male/female relationship, to which the tension of black/white roles is added- is only the climactic scarcity of the process. The apparently unequal sexual relationship between her and Dick is a symptom of the deeper abyss dividing them; she can only feel affection towards him when she is in a position of moral transcendence. Her own hollowness and impersonality are projected into the African servant; she is infuriated by his object like presence 'as if he were not really there, only a black body ready to do her bidding'. (Lessing 59)

At this stage in Mary's acknowledged self-disdain, the black servant Moses enters her life. As a man, Moses exudes a sexual power that Mary has been unconsciously seeking for; but as a black person, he must be controlled, subordinated to her will. Gradually such a strange and intense friendship out of rivalry is built between them that Moses becomes the personification of Mary's self-hatred. The more intensely she realizes she is losing power over him, the more she asserts that whatever power is left on her she would use it by making unreasonable demands on him. In *Black Skin White Mask* Frantz Fanon instantiates this condition:

The Negro enslaved by his inferiority; the white man enslaved by his superiority alike behave in accordance with a neurotic orientation. (Fanon 42)

During the years immediately after the Anglo-Boer wars, Britain set about unifying the four colonies including the former Boer republics into a single self-governed country called the Union of South Africa. Under the provisions of the South Africa Act 1909, the Union became an independent Dominion of the British Empire, governed under a form of constitutional monarchy, with the British monarch represented by a Governor-General. Among other harsh segregationist laws, including denial of voting rights to black people, the Union parliament enacted the 1913 Natives' Land Act, which earmarked only eight percent of South Africa's available land for black occupancy. White people, who constituted twenty percent of the population, held ninety percent of the land. As a consequence, the blacks were denied from their primary rights and they were bound to take shelter under white men's premises in the form of slaves or servants. Lessing could aptly present the prevalent apartheid (racial segregation in South Africa) through several black characters in *The Grass is Singing* (Thompson). This very flavor of apartheid is evident in *The Blood Knot*, where Athol Fugard remarks:

All my life had been spent in the shadow of apartheid. And when South Africa went through its extraordinary change in 1994, it was like having spent a lifetime in a boxing ring with an opponent and suddenly finding yourself in that boxing ring with nobody else and realising you've to take the gloves off and get out, and reinvent yourself. (Fugard 56)

Mary-Moses's relationship can also be perceived in terms of master-slave relationship. On the political and sociological level, it replicates the instability between the oppressive white minority and the black majority in South Africa. Here, the notion of 'power' plays a significant role and on the physical level it reflects the shifting tensions of sexual dominance and submission between male and female. On the psychological level, it dramatizes the splits within the protagonist's fragmenting personality. Mary's psychic state at this point resembles what the British psychiatrist R.D. Laing calls 'engulfment' or 'implosion'.

The full terror of the experience of the world as liable at any moment to crash in and obliterate all identity as a gas will rush in and obliterates a vacuum...this happening

because he has come to feel that all he can be is the awful nothingness of just this very vacuum(Laing 45).

Homi K. Bhabha is the leading contemporary critic who tried to expose the opposition inherent in colonial discourse in order to highlight the colonizer's ambivalence in respect to his position toward the colonized other (Bhabha 85). Like all the whites, Mary and Dick perceived Moses as the colonial other just because of his race, culture and seemingly dark complexion. The discourse puts pressure on the white colonizers and this affects the lives of Mary and Dick Turner. They are in a way turned into a colonial 'other' as they cannot live as the discourse asks them to. The colonizing force did not only control the black population but also the colonizers were making life impossible for the Turners. One can quite clearly see that Mary and Dick struggle to live up to the demands of the discourse and hence they counter the prevalent colonial discourse.

Mary tends to develop an "intense emotional ambivalence" towards Moses (Georgescu 27), and Moses turns into a projection of her repressed passions. Throughout the centuries, colored men and women are not seen as humans, they are only objectified as a sexual commodity.

Remembering that thick black neck with the lather frothing whitely on it, the powerful back stooping over the bucket, was like a goad to her. (Lessing 125)

Mary used to treat Moses as an obstruction: "a machine without a soul" (Lessing 132).

Unlike other natives, Moses calls her "madame" and follows "his desire to please her", to hear an approving word from her. In fact, in Fanon's words, the Negro wishes to be taken as white and it is only a white woman who can do so by loving him and proving that he is worthy of white love (Fanon 45). In some portion of the novel, fatherly gestures are found on Moses' character in spite of the fact that it was Moses who had ruthlessly faced Mary's whippings on his face when he was working in the field. In Freudian terms, Mary's intimate passion for her father is replaced with inclination toward Moses, that is the primary "incestuous taboo is substituted by the colonial taboo" (Georgescu 29). This incestuousness led Mary the most to fall for Moses. Moses has been trying to please the white lady in order to secure his self-identity, ultimately failed when he is dismissed by certain circumstances. Mary was only the messiah of his ever-

deprived life. In *The Wretched of the Earth* Fanon aptly shows how a native yearns to get equal to their masters:

When the native is confronted with the colonial order of things, he finds he is in a state of permanent tension. The settler's world is a hostile world, which spurns the native, but at the same time it is a world of which he is envious. (Fanon 27)

Moses's only ray of hope got shattered when Charlie Slatter takes over the Turner's farm. When he found out that Dick and Mary were leaving the farm forever, he became desperate to retrieve his lost sense of power over Mary and yearns to take revenge on the submissive who has dared to be herself once again. Charlie provisionally hired Tony Marston in order to manage the farm. Moses could foresee the separation when Charlie and Tony both went against him and Mary was changed into a turncoat. Societal pressure and Slatter's involvement made the alienation possible and this turned Moses to a beast. In the 'Bible' Moses is presented as the Hebrew prophet and a messiah (Deuteronomy, Acts 3:22ff), paradoxically, in postcolonial world this name is attributed to a murderer.

Although no apparent motives were found behind the murder, but if it came down to forensics it would be clear that the killer was Moses and his real intention was to loot the valuables. Various critics have expressed confusion over why the dialectic must necessarily be resolved by Moses's murder of Mary. A reviewer in *The Doris Lessing Newsletter* asked, "why does Moses murder Mary?", "why does he feel he has to kill her?" Lessing leaves Moses's inner state shrouded in mystery. Mary suffered from guilt of betraying Moses. She suffered from paranoia and hallucination and as a result of it she fell ill:

`I have been ill for years,' she said tartly. `Inside, somewhere. Inside. Not ill, you understand. Everything wrong, somewhere. (Lessing 175)

Even before Moses approached to kill her, she could feel her presence. Mary herself becomes complicit in her own murder. Mary's murder, portrayed from a black man's perspective, is the revenge for the betrayal: "And then the bush avenged itself". Moses appeared before Mary as a natural calamity:

Then, as she heard the thunder growl and shake in the trees, the sky lit up, and she saw a man's shape move out from the dark and come towards her. (Lessing 178)

And if we perceive the murder from the white woman's perspective, it is her inferiority complex, dependency complex and duplicity which killed her. If Moses had not killed Mary, she would have killed herself. It would be biased to blame only Moses for the murder since it is he who gave her relief by taking away her psychologically injured life. Thus, Moses acts as the murderer as well as the deliverer of Mary.

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